

Synthetic Dataset Generation for Change Detection in Mining Areas Using Image Inpainting

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Abstract: Change Detection is a critical task in Remote Sensing, aimed at identifying and quantifying alterations in a specific area over time by analyzing satellite or aerial imagery. While numerous datasets and models have been developed for this purpose, most existing benchmarks focus primarily on urban or agricultural environments, neglecting the particular challenges of mining areas. Moreover, ground truth data in current datasets tend to be coarse and insensitive to small-scale modifications, reducing their suitability for precise applications such as environmental monitoring or land-use management in mining zones. To address this limitation, this work presents the creation of a custom synthetic dataset for Change Detection tailored to mining areas, generated using inpainting techniques to simulate realistic temporal variations in satellite imagery. This paper details the dataset creation pipeline, discusses challenges encountered during the inpainting process, and analyzes the suitability of synthetic data generation. Experimental results demonstrate that models trained with the proposed synthetic data achieve improved sensitivity to small-scale changes compared to baseline datasets. Overall, the main contribution of this work is the proposal and evaluation of a controlled synthetic data generation strategy for Change Detection in mining areas.

Keywords: change detection; bitemporal analysis; area of interest; inpainting; synthetic dataset.

1 Introduction

Change Detection (CD) is a fundamental problem in Remote Sensing (RS) and computer vision that involves identifying differences in the state of a geographic area over time (Cheng et al. 2023). By comparing two or more temporally separated images of the same location, CD methods aim to detect changes caused by natural events, human activities, or environmental factors. In the context

of satellite imagery, these changes can include urban expansion, deforestation, flooding, agricultural activity, and mining operations.

The development of deep learning-based approaches for CD has led to significant advances in performance, however, these models heavily rely on the availability of large, annotated datasets. Most public datasets such as LEVIR-CD (Chen and Shi 2020) or DSIFN (Xu et al. 2024) are designed around urban or suburban landscapes, where the primary changes are related to building and road construction. Consequently, these datasets do not adequately represent other types of land cover transformations, particularly those that occur in mining regions, which exhibit distinct textures and spatial patterns.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Challenges in Change Detection Dataset Creation

Creating a high-quality dataset for CD is challenging due to the need for accurately co-registered multi-temporal image pairs and the time-consuming, often subjective process of generating ground truth labels (Figure 1). Additionally, existing datasets are typically insensitive to subtle changes, relying on coarse binary definitions that fail to capture fine-grained alterations such as small excavations, erosion, or gradual terrain deformation (Ji et al. 2024). This limitation is further exacerbated by their focus on urban environments, reducing their effectiveness for applications in mining and other natural or semi-natural settings.

2.2 Motivation and Objective

Given these limitations, one of the objectives of our work was to design a custom synthetic dataset for CD specifically focused on mining areas. Instead of relying solely on manually annotated real-world data, the proposed

Figure 1. LEVIR-CD, a classic urban CD dataset (Chen and Shi 2020).

approach generates synthetic temporal image pairs using image inpainting methods. The core idea is to take a satellite image of a mining area and artificially introduce controlled modifications that simulate realistic temporal changes such as pit expansion, new waste deposits, and stockpile growth without altering the overall visual characteristics of satellite imagery. This synthetic data can then serve as a training set for CD models, enabling better generalization to mining contexts.

2.3 Methodology

2.3.1 Study Sites and Data Acquisition

For the creation of a mining-specific CD dataset, four distinct mining areas in Spain were selected as study sites, each representing unique mineral extraction activities and environmental conditions. Satellite imagery for these Areas of Interest (Aois) was collected from the Copernicus Sentinel-2 database (ESA 2026) due to its adequate spatial resolution, coverage, and visual quality. The Sentinel-2 imagery was accessed following the standard data retrieval procedures provided by the Copernicus program. Although Sentinel-2 provides additional spectral bands that may be informative, we only extracted the RGB (red, green, blue) bands to keep the method architecture-agnostic and to evaluate the contribution of synthetic data independently of multispectral feature engineering:

- Canteras (Granada, Spain, 37.103842, -3.691592, Figure 2): an open-pit mine exploiting the Monte vive celestine deposit, the largest in Europe.
- Tharsis, San Telmo and La Zarza (Huelva, Spain, 37.596544, -7.110303; 37.800439, -6.968322; 37.709639, -6.853944): historical mining areas focused on pyrite extraction, characterized by open pits, waste deposits, and occasional water bodies.

2.3.2 Inpainting-Based Dataset

Synthetic temporal variations were generated using inpainting techniques, a method that can reconstruct, modify, or add content to images, on satellite imagery of mining areas. For each site, two reference images (from 2017 and 2025) were used as bases for generating synthetic variations. This time gap was chosen to represent potential long-term changes in mining activity.

Two models were tested during experimentation: Flux Kontext Dev (Labs et al. 2025) and Qwen Image Edit (2026), with the latter being used predominantly due to its better ability to preserve spatial realism in satellite imagery. For each base image, multiple inpainted variations were generated using textual prompts simulating typical mining changes, such as adding stockpiles, expanding activity, or creating small roads, producing realistic scenarios of mining evolution over time. Due to the stochastic nature of generative models, images were discarded after manual inspection if they exhibited: (i) unrealistic textures or artifacts, (ii) geographically implausible modifications, or (iii) poor visual integration between the inpainted region and the original image. The process resulted in over 900 images suitable for inclusion in the dataset.

Figure 2. On the left, the base 2017 image of the Canteras mine. On the right, four inpainting examples obtained using Qwen Image Edit. The modifications are highlighted with dashed white circles.

2.3.3 Change Map Generation

Change maps were initially generated using a pixel-wise differencing approach between each base image and its inpainted variants. The absolute difference was thresholded to produce binary masks, but this method proved unreliable: low thresholds introduced excessive noise, while higher thresholds removed actual inpainting changes. Change maps were manually created using GIMP: masks were created as binary layers aligned with the corresponding RGB image, using a constant brush size and zoom level. The masks were carefully painted to accurately match the inpainting modifications and then exported using the same resolution and coordinate alignment as the original Sentinel-2 patches to ensure consistency.

After change maps were created, each accepted inpainted image underwent a secondary modification stage intended to increase visual variability. Adjustments included modifications to lighting, hue, saturation, gamma, and contrast. Although Deep Learning-based augmentation was considered, simple deterministic image processing using OpenCV (2026) proved faster and sufficient for the intended effects. These operations were applied only after the change masks had been finalized.

Clouds were not added synthetically, as the dataset intentionally excludes cloudy scenes. Shadow manipulation was also omitted because shadows are negligible at the satellite nadir angles used for these images.

2.3.4 Dataset Splitting

The dataset follows a 70/20/10 split for training, validation, and testing. Synthetic samples generated from the same base image were assigned to the different subsets according to this split, resulting in each subset containing variants from all base scenes (Figure 3). After processing, the dataset was organized following a standard supervised CD structure.

2.4 Model Architecture

MineNetCD (Yu et al. 2024) is a Deep Learning framework for CD using RS imagery in mining environments. It is part of a benchmark that includes a large-scale dataset and a unified framework for evaluating CD methods. It features a Siamese architecture where two identical encoders extract

Figure 3. Subset of the generated dataset: from left to right, unaltered duplicates of the original 2017 Canteras images from the Copernicus Sentinel-2 mission via the Copernicus Open Access Hub, images modified via inpainting, and the corresponding change ground truths. The mining area corresponds to the brighter, irregular-shaped excavation zone located at the center of the images and its surroundings.

features from image pairs, which are then processed by a ChangeFFT module using Fast Fourier Transform to detect subtle frequency-domain variations, before a decoder generates the final binary change map. The framework's official repository (AI4RS 2026) provides the necessary scripts and pretrained models to enable fine-tuning on custom datasets.

The MineNetCD framework utilizes two architectures that were fine-tuned using the synthetic dataset: Swin_Diff_B (Liang et al. 2025), based on the Swin Transformer, and ResNet_Diff_50 (He et al. 2015).

3 Results

After training and fine-tuning the models using the synthetic dataset within the MineNetCD framework (Figure 4), inference was performed on the corresponding test set. Each obtained model, generated by varying hyperparameters and testing the available architectures, was evaluated based on its ability to generate accurate and spatially coherent change maps while minimizing false positives and correctly identifying areas of mining expansion or material displacement.

The performance of the models was assessed using standard CD metrics: (Precision, Recall, F1-score, and IoU,

Table 1), computed on the synthetic test set with available ground truth change maps (Figure 5). In this work, particular attention is given to F1-score and IoU.

4 Discussion

Among all evaluated configurations, ResNet_1e-4_CM_50 (ResNet-50, Learning Rate 1e-4, 50 steps, with Channel Mixing) achieved the best overall results. The obtained metric values fall within the range typically reported by other CD models in their respective evaluation settings, supporting the validity of our results. In contrast, alternative models applied to our images failed to generalize, producing either blank masks or excessive noise, highlighting their limited ability to generalize to the characteristics of our data. These experiments suggest that synthetic data generated via inpainting is a viable strategy for specialized CD, as shown by the significant improvement in spatial coherence when comparing model predictions before and after training.

Figure 4. ResNet-50 architecture. In the CD configuration, each temporal image is processed independently, and the resulting features are compared to generate a difference map that is decoded into a binary mask (TERRAVISION project 2026).

Table 1. Results for a sample of the evaluated models in terms of Precision, Recall, F1-score, and IoU. The best-performing model (highlighted in the table) is ResNet_1e-4_CM_50, followed by Swin_5e-5_50.

Model	Precision	Recall	F1	IoU
ResNet_5e-5_50	0.861488	0.871294	0.866363	0.764233
ResNet_5e-5_100	0.89229	0.838944	0.864795	0.761796
ResNet_5e-5_150	0.909873	0.836687	0.871747	0.772652
ResNet_1e-4_CM_50	0.919595	0.836247	0.875943	0.779269
ResNet_1e-4_CM_100	0.916919	0.83362	0.873288	0.775076
ResNet_1e-4_CM_150	0.912393	0.83678	0.872952	0.774547
SWIN_5e-5_50	0.903834	0.84793	0.87499	0.777762
SWIN_5e-5_100	0.884263	0.84518	0.86428	0.760997

Figure 5. Example of model results for the Canteras mine.

From left to right: the reference image from 2017, the corresponding image from 2025, the binary change map generated by the CD framework, and an overlay of the detected changes on the 2025 image (mainly paths and changes in terrain).

5 Conclusions

This work, conducted within the framework of the European project TERRAVISION (2026), presented a synthetic dataset generation pipeline for CD in mining areas based on image inpainting techniques. The resulting dataset may facilitate the training of Deep Learning models aimed at detecting subtle surface changes that are often overlooked in existing CD benchmarks. Experimental results suggest that models fine-tuned on the proposed dataset can achieve promising performance, with the ResNet_1e-4_CM_50 configuration yielding the best results among the evaluated models.

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